

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

COMPARING THE EVIDENCE OF INFLATION TARGETING IMPACT IN EMERGING ECONOMIES

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Abstract

Inflation targeting is adopted by countries which are emerging and furthermore developing but also by industrialized economies. Many studies are conducted to understand how inflation targeting has impacted growth and development. Even though this study itself is based on emerging economies, we decided to compare the research result of different group of countries. The historical data has shown that for most of the countries, inflation targets were rarely reached. Generally different countries and macroeconomic conditions face different deviations, but for most of the cases, the largest ones are strongly related with exchange rate volatility. But other reasons might relate with possible external and internal shocks. The internal shocks mainly relate with the macroeconomic conditions, lack of co-ordination of monetary and fiscal policy, or any other possible domestic crises. While the external ones relates with the global financial crises, volatility of the fuel prices, inflows and outflows volatility due to risk sensitivity.

Keywords: Inflation targeting, emerging economies, central bank, policy.

1. Introduction

Inflation Targeting is a monetary policy framework that targets inflation directly without using an intermediary target. The main goal is to settle a target and achieve it within a specific period. New Zealand was the first country that in 1989 adopted inflation targeting. After that industrialized countries like Canada, United Kingdom, Australia and Finland joined shortly. During the last couple of years, the literature has been focusing more on the adoption of inflation targeting by the emerging markets rather than the industrialized ones. Inflation targeting application is different from country to county but commonly these countries all apply the same four elements: 1. Aim to achieve price stability 2. Set a numerical target 3. Defines the horizon of the time needed to reach this target 4. Constantly evaluates if the goal is achieved and adjusting accordingly the short-term interest rate, which is the main monetary policy instrument. Mishkin, (2000) During the last two and a half decades, inflation targeting has been the monetary policy framework choice of many countries.

2. Advantages and Disadvantages of Inflation Targeting

2.1 Advantages of Inflation Targeting

Starting to discuss about the advantages of inflation targeting, we should keep in mind that such a framework has lower cost compared to other policies. The failure of this policy as argued by Nicoletta Batini et al., (2005) leads to very short term cost which do not strongly impacts the debt, reserves or even the crises. The losses might be seen in the increasing inflation and even a slow economic growth, but always for a short or

medium term. leads to very short term cost which do not strongly impacts the debt, reserves or even the crises. The losses might be seen in the increasing inflation and even a slow economic growth, but always for a short or medium term.

One of the best characteristics of inflation targeting is that it directly targets inflation, without the need and the usage of an intermediary variable. It is crucial for the central banks to define the target and the time horizon as clearly as possible.

This whole process will make the central banks more credible from the public point of view. Having the tools to make clear predictions and forecast about inflation directly affects the public. So another important characteristic of inflation targeting is that it promotes transparency of the central bank to the public. Since this framework is much easily understandable and it impacts the economy directly through the expectations, central banks find it essential to communicate and present the whole process of targeting. This framework places the focus on mainly what the central bank can achieve rather than what they fail to achieve. In other words, such a framework aims at price stability and does not focus on other variable such as output or unemployment rate. This fact makes the bank more credible.

Apart from increasing the credibility of the central bank the communication to the public is a very successful way of affecting the inflation expectations. When the target is understandable, and most importantly if it is clear and realistic, the expectations from the public for inflation will almost match the forecasted inflation. This leads to price stability and as a whole the aim of the central bank is easily reached.

Apart from the transparency and credibility inflation targeting encourages central banks to be more accountable from the public point of view, since such targets encourage the public to support the independency of the central banks. The other aspect of transparency is related with the government. It does not matter the type of the policy that a country has chosen, there should always be a balance between fiscal policies and the monetary ones. But it is essential for the central bank to be independent completely from other institutions especially for countries which have been having monetary policies management issues through the years. This independency allows space for the central banks to put as a key and primary goal the price stability and leave aside other goals.

Mishkin,(2001) focuses also on the advantage that inflation targeting has on relation to the time- inconsistency trap. Inflation targeting decreases the changes of timeinconsistency trap, making the central bank more accountable. The reason why is related with the fact that inflation targeting targets a numerical value of inflation as a primary and priority goal, making so the central bank more accountable. This target is set once and remains the same over time, no matter what the conditions of the economy are. As argued by Mervyn King, (2004) "Inflation targeting is a framework designed for a world of learning".

2.2 Disadvantages of Inflation Targeting

Disadvantages of inflation targeting are commonly highlighted especially after the crises in 2008 – 2009.

One of the greatest concerns not only for inflation targeting but for any other framework is the relation with the fiscal policy. For a monetary policy to be fruitful and reach the target results the environment should be stable but also there should be no contradiction between it and the fiscal policy.

As argued by (Debelle (1997) if an economy is facing huge public debt the failure of the inflation targeting as a framework is highly expected. The reason behind is that the public debt encourages an increasing inflation, which strongly contradicts the main goal of inflation targeting. Mishkin & Savastano, (2001)state that for such a framework to work accordingly the economy should be financially stable and most importantly no dominancy of fiscal policy should be seen.

In their paper Leeper & Leith,(2016)try to understand inflation as a joint monetary and fiscal phenomenon. They conclude that monetary and fiscal policies interact with private- business behavior to produce the aggregate level of price. Choosing between the monetary and the fiscal point of view for defining the inflation dynamics depends strongly on the circumstances and there is no way of saying which one is the right and which one is the wrong policy.

Another disadvantage of inflation targeting is related with the fact that inflation itself is not easily controlled by the central banks. Countries that suffer the most from this problematic are the economies which are emerging and growing and have a tendency of high inflation rate. This issue which is pointed out by F. S.

Mishkin,(1999)emphasis the difficulties of forecasting inflation rate under these circumstances. Countries, which prior were characterized by high inflation, will have a greater change on having a huge variance between what they are forecasting and what the level will be, affecting so directly the credibility of the banks itself. This whole process makes it even more difficult for the central banks to explain the situation to the public, causing so more problems. Savastano, et al.,(1997) states that the best scenario for the implementation of inflation targeting as a monetary policy framework is the case where the county itself has been having deflation periods prior to this policy.

3. Literature review

Comparing the evidence of Inflation targeting impact in both industrialized and emerging economies

On the paper written by Fraga et al.,(2003) we are faced with different outcomes for the emerging economies and for industrialized ones. A higher volatility is seen in emerging economies for inflation rate and the output, interest rate and the exchange rate as well. The authors tried to justify these changes through the through the differences that characterizes these two types of economies. Basically, emerging economies are facing problems with their institutions, they lack both stability and transparency but at the same time they are more exposed and sensitive to the stick of external shocks.

Mishkin, (2004) conclude that inflation targeting as a monetary policy is much more complicated in emerging economies and one of the biggest factors that encourage these complications relate with the exchange rate fluctuations. In another paper written together with Calvo in 2003 Calvo & Mishkin,(2003) they both point out their concerns for the decision of emerging economies to go with such policies that allow discretions to policy makers in the non-so favorable macroeconomic conditions and stability might as well lead to not desirable outcomes. As Fraga et al they agree that emerging economies are a bit more fragile to higher inflation and possible crises due to their weak institutions. In order for inflation targeting to be as successful as desired the economies should be characterized by very healthy and stable fiscal, monetary and financial institutions. They strongly point out the help that IMF can give in different ways to these economies.

Rose, (2006) tries to analyze the volatility of exchange rate by comparing inflation targeting and non-targeting economies. The study uses a dataset of 21 inflation targeting economies and 42 non-targeting ones, comparing them in terms of capital inflows and exchange rate volatility. The conclusions favor inflation targeting countries and show that by shifting to this monetary policy declines the amount of the unexpected stops in the capital inflows and a lower exchange volatility.

Mishkin & Schmidt-Hebbel, (2001) both conducted another research which compared for the period prior and after the adaptation 21 developed and emerging economies which target their inflation rate to a group of 13 countries which are not targeting inflation.

Using quarterly data for period 1989-2004 they concluded their results using panel impulse respond, difference in difference model and panel var. The outcomes show that countries which have adopted inflation targeting showed an initial average inflation rate of 12.6%, which later on declined to 6% in the converge phase to reach the final average of 2.3 % when meeting the stationary target. For industrial countries which have adopted inflation targeting framework compared to the ones which have not face a more volatile inflation rate but a lower inflation persistence. On the other hand the emerging economies both the output gap and the output volatility decline for target economies and the non-target ones but the output and inflation persistence is lower in inflation targeting emerging economies.

The relative most positive result for inflation targeting success as a framework are seen in studies that mainly relate with emerging economies. As mentioned above Lin & Ye,(2009) conducted a more advance research increasing the number of countries from 21 to 51 including emerging economies and a new timeline. The results show that the impact of inflation targeting as a monetary policy for emerging economies are quite positive, as the numerical results show that the decline to 3% in inflation rate is seen in the economies that are emerging. For developed countries these results are not considered to be significant.

While other studies mentioned above which are not in favor of adopting inflation targeting for emerging economies as these economies are not able to fully meet all the preconditions, Freedman & Laxton, (2009) reached to conclusions that actually none of the countries which adapted inflation targeting had all the preconditions fully met and that there is no significant importance of these preconditions in the improvements in macroeconomic aspect from pre to post adaptation of this policy. Though it is quite visible that there exists a gap in level of these achieved preconditions between the developed and emerging market economies, still this should not prevent the emerging market economies to take the leap and adopt inflation targeting.

Apart from this aspect their research results which was conducted based on 13 targeting and 29 non-targeting countries show that both the inflation rate and inflation volatility were declined but not at the extend of an output decline.

4. Inflation targeting in Emerging Economies

4.1 Inflation Targeting in Albania

Albania started the transition phase in 1991 and since then it has been progressing a lot considering that no pre-transition reform was taken before 1991. Of course, with the liberation of the economy the immediate effect was an increase in both unemployment and inflation rates together with a sharp decline in output, which respectively increased migration to neighbor countries. Another shock in the Albanian economy was seen right after the collapse of the pyramid schemes in 1997, when inflation and unemployment reached their maximum levels. The recovering process was better than expected in term of the statistics with an average

of 6% Real GDP increase and inflation targeting fluctuation around the target of 3%. If being compared to other countries which were in transition, Albania has performed much better in terms of stabilization of macroeconomic indicators, it managed to decline inflation rate from over 237% to 6% in 1996 and maintain it with very few fluctuations around the target of 3% for the following years, excluding here 1997 when the pyramidal schemes collapsed. This performance was an outcome of the restrictive monetary policy implemented by Bank of Albania. Adopting Monetary targeting regime as a monetary policy made Albania one of the few countries which implemented this regime. This regime in specific monitors M3 as an intermediate target and in this way it controls the money supply in the economy. What simulated mostly the usage of this monetary policy was the IMF technical assistance program which apart from monetary targeting targeted other indicators such as international reserve, total funding of the budget deficit and net internal means. Throughout the years in order to maintain stability and control the monetary supply, Bank of Albania used different instruments and tools both direct and indirect ones. Firstly, central bank settled a ceiling on the level of the credits provided by commercial banks which worked as a primary tool for the control of the monetary supply. A couple of years later, in 1995, central bank used the deposits rate of SOB's as an indirect instrument for controlling the monetary supply. Another attempt to influence interest rate after the removal of credit celling in 2000 was done through the open market operations, Repos. Even after taking into consideration all the positive results from the application of this monetary targeting policy regime, Bank of Albania had its own doubts related with the future application of it. As per Estrella & Mishkin, (1997) paper, such monetary targeting regime in times of price stability should not be a reliable regime for emerging economies. The reason behind it is related with the information that could be obtained from the monetary aggregates once inflation is maintained under the borders of the target. According to their results with stability of inflation rate, the velocity shock noises increase causing so the monetary aggregates to be less reliable. This could easily be demonstrated by the difference of planned and actual monetary aggregates and planned, and actual inflation rate expressed in % change. The divergence of M3 (broad money) has been an issue known and analyzed by the central bank, which together with other factors such as supply shocks exchange rate movements and the pressure that they forced on inflation rate encouraged central bank to consider other monetary policies. Without fully applying the IT, Albania has been classified by Carare & Stone, (2006) as an inflation targeting lite country.

The process of starting to adopt IT as a monetary policy regime started in early 2004 and was officially finalized on 2009, when the government announced Inflation Targeting as the official monetary policy regime. There are three main reasons behind this movement. Firstly, the unresponsive monetary aggregate to velocity shocks in an environment characterized by price stability, was quite a good signal for the Bank of

Albania to change the monetary policy regime from the existing one to Inflation Target regime. Secondly, the government would recognize the importance that all of the macroeconomic factors have in the successfully implementing this new, complex regime. Lastly previously used monetary target regime, was inspired by IMF technical assistance program and implementing a new monetary policy regime would independently encourage Bank of Albania to maintain stability through inflation targeting as a nominal anchor .

As many economists and researchers argue being used as a monetary policy the Inflation Targeting does not surely translate to stability and growth. There are other preconditions that should be met for this monetary policy to be successful. In other words the effectiveness of the Inflation Targeting should not only be measured by the approach that it has but also by including the function of those other factors such as the relationship between the central bank and the government, the autonomy and transparency of the central bank, the technical infrastructure in terms of analysis and forecasting, together with the stability of the financial environment. Marco Arnone, (2007) Carl. E. Walsh, (2006).

With all these factors combined together, is inflation targeting effective in the economic growth of the country? Based on previous studied, unfortunately

there is not a conclusive argument related to this question as different scholars, economists and researches have been showing through their studies different outcomes.

One of the greatest economist, M. Friedman argued through his research that "Inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon in the sense that it is and can be produced only by a more rapid increase in the quantity of money than in output". In order to understand better this statement, which now is being known as the Friedman Theory, inflation should be accepted as a phenomena caused by the expansion monetary policies. According to Friedman, there was no time in history that inflation and increase in money supply did not grow side by side. He argues that in the long run the monetary growth does increase inflation as well but not the output.

Studies made by F. S. Mishkin, (1990), Mishkin & Posen, (1997), Walsh, (2009) show empirical results that countries which have adopted inflation targeting as a monetary regime perform much better in the macroeconomic indicators point of view. Other studies like Robert J. Barro, (1995) and Judson & Orphanides, (1999) argue that the relation between inflation rate and economic growth is strongly negative.

Figure 1- Output Growth and Inflation Rate for Albania

Source: IMF webpage (World Economic Outlook download)

4.2 Inflation Targeting in Serbia

National Bank of Serbia announced Inflation targeting as the new monetary policy framework on September 2006. Other monetary policies were not that useful in terms of assuring stability of inflation rate. One of the main reasons behind this new monetary policy relates with inflationary shocks causes mainly from the shift that Serbian economy has now towards European Union and therefore the euroization which comes included in the package. As expected, the main goals of this new monetary policy relate with increase stability in the local currency, encourage low and stable inflation rate. Together with the inflation targeting another change in the existing policies related with exchange rate regime from fixed to flexible which would possibly reduce the effects of shocks. Generally, floating exchange rate regimes come together with the inflation targeting. The reason why relates with the fact that such regimes need a nominal anchor, and as exchange rate

cannot be one, then inflation rate is the winning candidate.

Before shifting to inflation targeting as a monetary policy, the inflation rate was relatively very high and for the first two years (2006 and 2007) inflation rate was maintained below the low target level. The main reason for this decline in inflation rate is the appreciation of the local currency. But slowly the inflation rate started to jump up again from 5.4 % to 10.1% in 2008. 2008 was not a good year not only for the National Bank of Serbia but also for most of the central banks that apply inflation targeting as their monetary policy regime. The external shocks such as the increase in the oil price encouraged the increase in the expected inflation. Apart from the external shocks, the lack of liquidity in the global markets and the local prices for agricultural products which doubled within year time together, another issue that troubled NBS was the depreciation of the local currency. With all the things going on the reference interest rate increased almost 6 time within a year range. Inflation pressure was almost

closed to the target by the time the economies in Europe were in the recession period. The depreciation of the local currency throughout all the period that is presented in the table plays a great role in achievement of the targets. Right after the stabilization of the rate in 2009, the depreciation of the local currency once again was reflected in the inflation rate of 2010 and 2011 which were higher compared to the target. The maximum rate was seen in 2012 where inflation rate was twice as much as the target inflation rate. The following years 2013 and 2014 were of low inflation due to the recession pressure, for most of the countries in Europe negative rates were seen. The target for 2015 and 2016 was 4% with a tolerance of $\pm 1.5\%$, meaning a low

level of 2.5% and a maximum of 5.5%. The target for 2017 was decreased by 1 percentage point. The reason for this decrease in the target relates with the decline in the risk of investments, improvements of the macroeconomic conditions and the stabilization of the global market. All this factor combined together with the decreasing trend of the achieved inflation from 2014 till 2016 has led the National Central Bank of Serbia to believe that Serbia has the potential to maintain the rates within the target. A lower inflation rate will serve better to the local currency, will decrease the currency risk and will furthermore stabilize the financial system in Serbia. (National Bank of Serbia)

Figure 2- Output Growth and Inflation Rate for Serbia

Source: IMF webpage (World Economic Outlook download)

4.3.1 Turkey

The macroeconomic situation in 2001 was characterized by a high public debt, high depreciation of the local currency, 67% inflation rate, and a failed tentative for long term adoption of a crawling exchange peg (which temporarily increased the credibility of the central bank). Turkey started applying inflation targeting in 2001 as a respond to the whole macroeconomic situation as a tentative salvation from the financial crises, the need to decline inflation rate, reduce the public debt and stabilize the prices and the local currency. For the following 4 years, up to 2005 Turkey was applying as a monetary policy implicit inflation targeting. The reason why it was called implicit relates with the fact that as a nominal anchor the base money was still being used and the preconditions such as the low level of inflation and development of a consistent and trustful inflation forecasting systems were not fully achieved. From 2006 till 2010 the full-fledged IT was applied. Inflation by the end of this phase started to decline to comparable values with Emerging and Developing Europe countries. Inflation rate through the time of the application of IT remained on average much more compared to Emerging and Developing Europe countries, but extremely felt in average as a single digit number. The target for 2018-2020 is set to 5% with a border of a plus minus 2 percentage points. The central bank maintains the same target even though for the last 6 year it was not met. (Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey)

4.3.2 Romania

Romanian economy was characterized from a very high inflation rate since 90's which declined to single digits only in 2004. Inflation targeting was introduced in 2005 and by then the Central bank knew exactly the focus: stabilization of the inflation rate. By the time that inflation targeting was adopted the National Bank of Romania has already been advancing in terms of benefiting from the independence in operational terms from the government, decline in the fiscal dominance, inflation rate reporting becoming more frequent, increase in the credibility and the exchange rate compatibility with IT. The targets for 2007 was 4% with a band of ($\pm 1.5\%$) and for 2008 it was 3.8%. For 2009 and 2010 the target was 3.5% and in 2011 and 2012 it declined to 3% with a $\pm 1\%$ boarder flexibility. Starting from 2013 up to now the inflation target is 2%. There were two main phases identified in the inflation targeting process for the National Bank of Rumania. The phase of declining inflation targeting which started with a target of 7% and ended up in 2012 with a target of 3%, this phase aimed the annual sustainable inflation rate. And the second phase is the multi-annual inflation phase with started in 2013 and continues up to 2018. This phase works as an intermediary phase to the final phase of long term inflation targeting. (National Bank of Romania)

4.3.3 Georgia

Prior to adopting inflation targeting as a monetary policy, National Bank of Georgia (NBG) was relying on monetary targeting. Theoretically if there would be a perfect relation between the money supply and the inflation rate, this regime would be very much preferred.

But in the real world and in the Georgian economy, money demand was not that stable causing so issues with the inflation rate. On the other hand the local currency depreciated and no matter how much the central bank tried, moving to a new monetary policy regime was a much preferable solution. So, Georgia announced inflation targeting as a monetary policy in 2009. In medium-term target which should be achieved for 2018-2020 inflation target is set to be 3%. Though the year inflation targeting reached its peak in 2008 with a rate of 9.95 which declined sharply the next year, just to jump right up again in 2010 and 2011 to 7.1% and 8.5% respectively. IMF (2007), (National Bank of Georgia)

4.3.4 Hungary

Inflation targeting for Hungary has been adapted since 2001. The main reason for such a shift in regimes related with the currency fluctuations. Prior to 2001, the central bank due to the exchange rate regime (which was adopted since 1995) was allowing a currency fluctuation of only 2.5%. This band was increased to 30% and this was seen as the very first step for the shift from an exchange rate regime to the inflation rate regime. The transition to the Inflation Targeting was gradual. Hungary joined European Union, but also it adopted the Euro. Joining European Union and Eurozone made Hungary automatically part of the Exchange rate mechanism (ERM 2), which forced the exchange rate to be as close as possible to the central parity. Still as central bank two main aims were target, stable inflation rate and stable exchange rate. Out of these two goals the price stability was the primary one. Characterized by transparency and accountability inflation target regime was identified from central bank to be the best regime framework to reach the nominal stability. Generally, the Hungarian inflation rate was not that much fluctuating and up to the adoption of inflation targeting the average rate was 18% with a declining trend. And from 2001 till 2016 the average inflation rate is around 4.4%. IMF (2007), (Magyar Nemzeti Bank)

4.3.5 Poland

Poland in order to grow the monetary aggregate (M2) adopted a fixed exchange rate regime and fixed the local currency to dollar. In most of the times the target was missed. The local currency real exchange rate appreciated and this forced the central bank to change the monetary policy in order to prevent the furthermore weakening of the external position of Poland's economy. First the fixed peg was used which was fast substituted by the crawling peg regime with 1.8 crawling rate. From 1991 to 1998 the authorities were switching to targeting from short-term interest rate, to reserve money, again to back short-term interest rates. In 1998 the new regime suggested by the Council was inflation targeting. This new monetary policy came with a lot of benefits. First of all since one of the main characteristics is transparency, the credibility towards the central bank was earned rapidly. But on the other hand the central bank knew exactly that there were some limitations coming together with this regime, such as the absence of a monetary and a fiscal policy which were co-ordinated together, lack of fully accessibility to the necessary information which captures the reaction of inflation rate to this new regime. But apart

from all of these differences still Poland managed to maintain a relatively stable and low inflation rate compared to countries in the Emerging and Developed Europe.

4.3.6 Czech Republic

Czech Republic adopted inflation targeting in 1997 right after giving up on the fixed exchange rate regime which was chosen to be the monetary policy framework since 1991. The reason behind this shift related strongly to the instability of the local currency which later led to the increasing inflation rate. The increasing trend of inflation rate caused huge problems with the trust toward the Czech National bank, another reason why this central bank decided to adopt inflation targeting as a monetary policy. By anchoring inflation rate, the Czech National Bank managed to decrease inflation rate from average 12.17 % before adoption phase to only average 2.49% (1998-2016). The trend of inflation rate responds to the financial crises and after words is the same as in the European countries.

4.3.7 Armenia

The inflation rate for Armenia was double digits till the late 1999. The Central Bank of Armenia announced the transition phase for inflation targeting in early 2006. With the announcement of this transition the Central Bank of Armenia made the decision to adopt inflation targeting as a monetary policy rather than exchange rate regime. This soothed the inflation rate within a short period of time increasing so the credibility in the central bank and reaching a stable macroeconomic environment. Inflation rate showed a huge increase during the financial crises but was once again stabilized in 2015 with a decline to 3.7% from 9% in 2008 when the crises hit the economy. From the same point of view the output growth faced a sharp decline, reaching below the average of the region in early crises phase. (IMF)

5. Conclusions

The historical data has shown that for most of the countries, inflation targets were rarely reached. Generally different countries and macroeconomic conditions face different deviations, but for most of the cases, the largest ones are strongly related with exchange rate volatility, such as the Serbian case. But other reasons might relate with possible external and internal shocks. The internal shocks mainly relate with the macroeconomic conditions, lack of co-ordination of monetary and fiscal policy, or any other possible domestic crises. While the external ones relates with the global financial crises, volatility of the fuel prices, inflows and outflows volatility due to risk sensitivity.

Two of the oldest countries that adopted inflation targeting in this group are Czech Republic and Poland. Both countries inflation rates fluctuated closely around the targeting values especially starting from 2003. In the case of the Poland generally the inflation rate was below the lower bound, forcing so the central bank to readjust the target after it was initially set in 1998.

Albania and Georgia adopted the inflation targeting in 2009. For most of the cases within this time range of almost 9 years the target for Albania was mainly

within the borders and the central bank did not adjust it any further, 3% with a border of $\pm 1\%$. As per the Georgian economy the target was adjusted and after the financial crises it was far below the border, picked up far above the border after 2011 and again declined below zero in 2014. For the last couple of years, the average inflation rate has been 3%, finally now within the target of central bank for 2018-2020.

Turkey, Serbia and Armenia adopted inflation target in 2001, 2007 and 2006 respectively. For all the three cases the inflation rate was very volatile and missing the target for most of the years. The main cause of this volatility relates to the depreciation of the local currency which led to two-digit inflation for Turkey and for some specific years also for Serbia. Average inflation rate for Turkey is around 8% for the last three years, above the target which for 2018-2020 is set to be 5% and only 1.5% for the Serbian economy, which has a target of midpoint 3% with a tolerance of $\pm 1.5\%$. For the Armenian economy the inflation rate was far above the target for most of the years between the 2009 and 2011.

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